

digiNEB White Paper

on the future of NEB in Horizon Programmes

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Editor's note

This White Paper is written in response to the European Commission working paper 'First Reflections on Building Blocks for the Design of a Possible EU Mission on the New European Bauhaus'. The contributing authors are thought leaders from the digiNEB community – the digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus. They include members of the digiNEB External Advisory Board and leaders of NEB Lighthouse projects. Representatives of this community first came together during the digiNEB event NEB@CERN 27 February – 1 March 2023 and, in a series of workshops, started to develop a comprehensive vision for the development of the New European Bauhaus digital ecosystem. A productive meeting about the NEB Mission was organised by digiNEB with representatives from the NEB unit at the JRC in Zagreb on the 20th and 21st of September, 2023. This White Paper starts by referring to the original vision by President von der Leyen and the Concept Paper by the NEB High Level Round Table (HLRT) and proceeds to the contributions of the listed authors.

We adopted a pluralistic approach to capturing the voices of the community, representing sometimes differing views, and most importantly, not cancelling each other out. Each EAB member or lighthouse leader who was asked to contribute was tasked with creating a 1-2 pager on their positioning in respect of the NEB Mission. Each positioning was added as a separate chapter. Contributors could work together or amplify each other's vision, by agreement with the authors. Aside from small edits, contributions are left intact demonstrating a multiplicity of views and diversity of approaches. All are valid, and seldom contradictory. We have at times suggested more effective wording to convey the message, but we have allowed for a democratic representation of all the core voices from the community.

Framing the NEB vision

When President von der Leyen launched the New European Bauhaus in her inaugural State of the Union speech on the 16th of September 2020, it was the first time that she called for a *"co-creation space where architects, artists, students, engineers, designers work together"*. This call to create a multidisciplinary movement for co-creation is significant because, for the first time, she called for **translation of thought into practice** through the **prototyping of tangible solutions** that could turn into **evidence-based policy**.

A group of practitioners were invited as the President's High Level Round Table to translate their practice into a Concept for the New European Bauhaus. The first HLRT activity identified a strong **"line of justice"** that cut through all foundational values. Mapping desired outcomes was united by a strong concept of **"learning by doing"**. Social justice and

knowledge exchange through hands-on practice was, therefore, very much at the heart of the initiative from the start.

For the HLRT, it wasn't just a case of translating their practice into the concept; it was also about **demonstrating it hands-on**, with some extraordinary examples. When the Ukrainian war broke out, architect Shigeru Ban and the Polish HLRT representative Hubert Trammer were on the ground on the border with Ukraine while 2 million people were crossing over into Poland in the first two weeks of the conflict. They assembled the Voluntary Architects Network to teach them how to create privacy shelters for immigrant families housed inside large hangars and sports halls. This knowledge was passed on and spread from the Polish border with Ukraine to the Slovakian borders, where volunteers fitted more shelters.

Another extraordinary example is the work of Sheela Patel. She works with women's collectives in informal settlements. One billion people are living in informal settlements around the world, and yet research into dwellings seldom considers this as a priority challenge. Sheela runs a project called "Roof Over Our Heads", which teaches how to build resilient, low-carbon, affordable homes. She embodies the idea of a **"beyond-European perspective"** that the HLRT deemed extremely important. To reinforce this perspective, the HLRT onboarded three more extraordinary people: Francis Kéré, Pritzker Prize winner for architecture from Burkina Faso; Nigerian-born Emeke Ogboh, an artist based in Berlin, and Ugandan activist Hilda Nakabuye.

The HLRT Concept Paper advocated for **radical inclusion**, where we are not divided into categories, but instead, we are encouraged to **focus on where we converge**. When we bring all kinds of domains together, **we don't cancel each other out**, but we respect and admire all the different knowledge and cultures that are brought to the table.

It is important also to acknowledge that humans are part of nature, and that our interdependence with the living environment including other species matters also for the large societal transformation. So from the beginning, the NEB HLRT promoted the idea of **"more-than-human ecosystems"**.

In practice, we have challenged urban planning and traditional approaches to land and infrastructure management and looked at ways in which we can plan by including living ecosystems in a novel research topic called **"Ecosystem Living"**. This requires research and innovation in situ, **to each region according to its needs**. The idea of **place-based learning** is an integral part of this process.

The Floating University in Berlin – one of the winners of this year's New European Bauhaus prizes and also of the Golden Lion at the Venice Biennale two years ago – very much captures this idea of place-based learning and multidisciplinary knowledge exchange, but also, very importantly, it captures the **new knowledge** that results from these methods. One of the biggest challenges for the NEB mission is to demonstrate that these methods are much-needed for a sustainable and equitable future and that they are **an exceptional way of generating new knowledge**.

The digital ecosystem perspective

Culture and community-driven digital systems can turn neighbourhoods into giant testbeds for solutions to grand challenges.

Fifteen years ago, it was assumed that the internet was all about distributing information and providing downloads. Soon, it became apparent that the real value lay with content creators and uploads - commonly referred to as participatory culture. The same paradigm shift is required for data-enabled spaces in neighbourhoods. Culture doesn't exist only in the nodes and synapses of distribution networks – it thrives in all of the spaces in-between where citizens act as co-creators of information based on social and cultural protocols, where technology becomes an important element of new locally grounded experiential aesthetics. Cultural interaction is an essential component of data-driven systems in neighbourhoods. Communities are *the driving force* of the neighbourhood's digital content. Active engagement of communities with their digital infrastructure can result in innovative solutions for community living, the use of data-enabled environments as a collaborative interface with governments, and the emergence of new inclusive languages of interaction, novel behaviours and subcultures. Considering culture and community as the drivers of digital systems allows neighbourhoods to become giant testbeds for solutions to grand challenges.

Community neighbourhood testbeds using NEB methods allow for R&I to capture knowledge from a unique blend of diverse perspectives.

Unlike homogenous research, technology or industry focus groups, community neighbourhoods offer a unique blend of diverse perspectives for generating new knowledge. Community neighbourhoods are primarily trans-generational and require research considerations of the youngest and oldest beneficiaries for any solution. They frequently blend the experience of citizenship with the roles of employee and business owner, joining the private and public domain. As we transform these neighbourhoods into more inclusive and natural spaces, they also become places of experimentation that challenge the nature/culture divide and call for regenerative and nature-based approaches. In many neighbourhoods, vernacular knowledge can be combined with frontier technologies. Such opportunities also arise from other functions and infrastructures next to which these neighbourhoods and communities are located—ports, airports, industrial districts, technology hubs, etc. to name just some—that can have an impact on health and liveability in the neighbourhoods. Cross-cutting engagement among neighbourhoods across Europe can help address larger projects in a shared way.

Research results at the intersection of diverse perspectives can be published in recognised journals such as the CERN IdeaSquare Journal of Experimental Innovation¹. Community neighbourhoods can become the testbeds for what Latour called “the rejection of the discrete binaries of human/nonhuman, digital/material, subject/object, nature/culture, private/public, and individual/collective” - meaning that the NEB ecosystem works towards

¹ <https://e-publishing.cern.ch/index.php/CIJ/>

considering and uniting all diverse dimensions and interactions of communities and life and the larger context in which they are located.

Mission-oriented multidisciplinary research is more than best practice combined.

Intelligent cooperation is a phenomenal strategic skill and the heart of civilised coexistence and cultural evolution. Research that joins knowledge from various disciplines using the methodologies from the NEB community does not merely combine best practice from various disciplines but results in much more than the sum of its parts – it generates new knowledge and technological breakthroughs. This means that it can provide fast responses to the urgent environmental challenges with a level of advancement required to create sustainable solutions for grand missions.

The impacts of these collaborations include novel research directions and innovation methods, rapid upskilling and behavioural change, and many more that have been identified by the European Commission in the recent comprehensive research, analysis and report by the Knowledge Valorisation Communities of Practice. The Codes of Practice for knowledge valorisation of industry-academia collaboration and citizen engagement will be published by the end of 2023². The Code of Practice for the knowledge valorisation of intellectual property assets recommends participation in open innovation platforms which offer opportunities of open precompetitive public-private partnerships for cross-sectoral collaborations and knowledge exchange³.

Multidisciplinary and transdisciplinary collaboration allows for a greater understanding of societal value networks.

Working across disciplines generates valuable knowledge for the growing field of cross-domain digital systems that are required to manage transitions towards sustainable economies. Cross-domain systems are necessary for the effective management of closed-loop material/product life cycles and related material/product passports that have to traverse multiple domains and affect diverse stakeholders. The NEB programme can partner with initiatives such as Materials Commons, launched by DG RTD and AMI, that aims to create a broad community of material science stakeholders⁴. As part of these systems, multidisciplinary approaches by the NEB community can enable material use to be monitored and kept within the limits set by the Donut Economy Model. Cross-domain networks can reveal systemic risks and align on resilience strategies and systems for responsibility.

The core NEB values implemented with communities on the ground must be reflected in our digital systems.

For broader impacts, it is vital to learn how to join forces with other knowledge domains and bridge various modes of expression. To ensure that core societal values are embedded in cross-domain data-driven ecosystems, interoperability of data spaces needs to be supported by a series of enabling mechanisms, including systems of agreements (from international

²https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/research-area/industrial-research-and-innovation/eu-valorisation-policy/knowledge-valorisation-platform/thematic-focus/communities-practice-complete-their-work-co-create-codes-practice-industry-academia-collaboration_en

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32023H0499&qid=1678171231088>

⁴ https://www.ami2030.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/12/2022-12-09_Materials_2030_RoadMap_VF4.pdf

regulation to P2P contracts), systems of resilience (environmental sustainability and "Black Swan Event" resilience), systems of responsibility (Corporate Social Responsibility, Responsible AI, Ethics), and systems of beliefs (societal values, including handling of data biases, information sensitivity and provenance). Setting up enabling systems has major implications on how we extract value from collaboration. Integrating digital elements into physical spaces fundamentally alters the perception and experience of these places, presenting distinct ethical challenges. These emerging hybrid spaces are becoming as central to community interaction and discussion as social media platforms. In response to this, rather than adopting a top-down approach with stringent policies and regulations, it's more effective to integrate appropriate parameters within the digital systems themselves. This strategy guides behaviours through positive incentives and motivations, fostering a more organic and self-regulated environment.

Non-routine cognitive skills from design practice can safeguard the social and ethical dimension of technology in industrial applications.

Design contributes non-routine cognitive skills, which are essential for original and often breakthrough insights in environments supported by frontier technologies. Within research programmes, design-led prototyping environments therefore are best placed to lead experiments where the impact of frontier technologies – such as AI, deep learning, extended reality and brain-computer interfaces – can be tested in safe environments and challenges addressed before applications are deployed at scale. These experiments test the extent to which the technology enables or obstructs human agency, decision-making processes and accountability. In this sense, we see culture and design as safeguarding the social and ethical dimension of technology and alleviating risks for deployment of novel applications for industry.

Quality of experience of the lived environment must be included in all digital and data-enabled interactions stimulating virtuosities.

In NEB, aesthetics is equated with quality of experience. Currently, European funding programmes universally lack quality in digital user experience and interfaces for research and industry. Poor quality interfacing leads to greater divides: low digital literacy, exclusion of those who cannot work out how to navigate content, greater inequality in accessing information, loss of benefits or services, and damage to democratic processes. Successful interaction with digital systems improves accessibility but also increases affordances to innovate and develop virtuosities. Before the invention of the piano, there was no pianist virtuoso - the idea and the affordance didn't exist. This applies to all novel technologies we design: quality interaction creates novel affordances for communities and ecosystems alike. The NEB is uniquely well-placed to create a programme of excellence for interaction with our physical and virtual living environments.

Using NEB methods to prototype solutions in direct collaboration with industry can help transition to an Industry 6.0: Ecosystemic.

Our ambitions towards greater industrial sustainability demand a fast paradigm and behavioural shift towards sustainable ecosystems - a transition from Industry 5.0: Human-Centric to Industry 6.0: Ecosystemic. With the urgent transition of all industry to data-driven

systems, the pace of transition has been forced to speed up considerably. Experimentation with NEB communities points to some clear clues for best practice in system design and new interactions with frontier technologies – as valuable new knowledge for the industrial transition. Demonstrating results in direct collaboration with industry can contribute to evidence-based industrial policy and speed up the transition towards ecosystemic industrial strategies.

Ecosystem living can serve as a paradigm for research into beyond-human cohabitation and smart communities.

Ecosystem living is a way to reframe the concept of urban planning by questioning whether *urban* is a necessary (or even desirable) condition for human habitation. It transcends the idea of *spatial* planning since the focus of spatial planning is limited to the physical space and not the complex interactions between cohabiting species. It does not advocate for ecosystem *planning* because it does not seek to impose order, encourage extractive practices or create the conditions for entirely anthropocentric habitation. It considers human beings and their activities to be part of nature and not separate from it. True ecosystem living is about harmony, alignment and balance, and finding an entire value network within a holistic cohabitation. This balance must synthesise and integrate artistic practice, scientific research, traditional craft professions and local cultural practices. It follows that Smart Communities should, therefore, extend beyond human to the development of intelligent systems that can manage interdependencies of human and non-human natural ecosystems. This could be a path towards emphasising caring, nurturing, and contingency, enabling designers, architects, and engineers to think about systems as components of bigger assemblages and promote precarious flourishing over extinction.

Private partnerships can be incentivised by measuring the rate of community adoption of emerging market applications.

NEB communities operate at the heart of emerging cultures and subcultures. They are uniquely placed to participate in technology transfer to new and exciting cultural expressions and emerging market applications. Novel business models and new markets that emerge can be monitored through market adoption. Evaluation of market adoption can use Market Adoption Readiness Levels (MARLs), already adopted by the recommendations of the CONNECT Advisory Forum (CAF) from 2014 and quoted in industry literature⁵. Based on evaluations, the NEB programme can support the scaling of excellence from the ground up in partnership with regional private and public funding. Design-led solutions for industry can be linked to private investments while culture-led R&I can be linked to philanthropy with better and structurally embedded financing for NGOs, CCS and entrepreneurial micro-companies.

Connecting the grassroots communities from the regions with high-level policy strengthens the position of regional governments.

The periphery – the outlying European Regions – can now be considered the centre of where we face the biggest threats of climate change. For example, European coasts and the

⁵<https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/oa-edit/10.1201/9781003337966-5/internet-things-applications-future-manufacturing-john-soldatos-sergio-gusmeroli-pedro-malo-giovanni-di-orio>

understanding of seas and oceans are at the forefront of water system change and key to creating ecosystem living. The NEB Programme has the opportunity to prioritise research by communities who are currently poorly represented in the R&I programmes, including those that face geographical, cultural or economic barriers. With knowledge of regional ecosystem framework conditions, activists and project initiators on the ground, micro-companies from the culture and creative sectors, and private philanthropists who care for the preservation of local traditions and democracies are all valuable contributors to the creation of new knowledge and can promote regional interests strengthening the position of their regional governments. As a movement that is a bastion of democracy, NEB can scale intelligence from the outlying European Regions to the centre, connecting it directly to high-level policy.

Ensuring a critical perspective of the NEB would foster pluralistic visions of the future.

A critical review of the Bauhaus and NEB's would avoid perpetuating oppressive structures and instead foster pluralistic visions for the future. With its significant legacy in design and education, the original Bauhaus school faced scrutiny for its exclusionary practices and Eurocentric approach. Eurocentric modernity, as a concept that positions Europe as the center of the world, has had far-reaching impacts beyond its borders, fostering a worldview of human separation from nature and consequent exploitation of the environment and non-European cultures. The NEB must consider these legacies, acknowledging pluralistic approaches and the true impact of technology on diverse populations, striving to move beyond the exploitative mental models of Eurocentric modernity/coloniality. The NEB, while citing the original Bauhaus as a foundational influence, must contend with contemporary global movements aiming to dismantle symbols of imperialism and oppression. Such examples are manifested in contemporary design movements such as participatory design, humble design, and the degrowth movement. The NEB's broad definitions of beauty, sustainability, and inclusiveness do not explicitly address power structures or the possibility of plural interpretations. Critics argue that this vagueness might reproduce the myth of universalism, where a monolithic view of Europe prevails over its inherent diversity. Furthermore, the NEB's documents hint at the problematic notion of better living through technology, suggesting that new creations universally improve life, which critics say overlooks the diversity of needs and contexts. There's also concern that the NEB's ambition to spread its principles globally could perpetuate colonial dynamics. A critical stance is called for to ensure the NEB does not reinforce colonial capitalism and instead commits to an inclusive approach that effectively addresses climate change and embraces pluralistic solutions.

Culture-driven R&I

A Mission that aligns with and enhances the NEB Vision

As noted in the opening paragraph of the Working Paper, a key element of the NEB vision is to “leverage the power of culture, art and creativity for the transition.” (p.1). In its current form, the Working Paper falls significantly short of demonstrating how this key element of the NEB vision will be integrated into the proposed Mission. However, we also note that there is a predominant focus on the competitiveness and innovation of the construction industry. We therefore ask for the proposed Mission to valorise the role of the arts, culture and creativity in helping us to (re)imagine a collective future that is inclusive, sustainable and beautiful. The vitality of Europe’s artistic, cultural and creative sectors and spaces of learning is paramount to the success of the necessary transition.

First and foremost, culture and participation in cultural activities are at the very heart of democracy, civic engagement and social cohesion, as evidenced in a recent independent report on Culture and Democracy (European Commission, 2023). Investing in culture has demonstrable positive correlations with civic engagement and democratic outcomes in communities across the EU. This is even more pressing at a time when the climate crisis risks further eroding trust in democracy, while also exacerbating inequalities.

Second, creativity is an essential ingredient of the competencies needed for a green transition. As recently highlighted in GreenComp: the European sustainability competence framework, creativity supports exploratory thinking, which in turn is a key competence in informing and envisioning sustainable futures and acting for sustainability (Joint Research Centre, 2022). Creativity is an essential component of future literacy, together with science and values for sustainability.

Third, culture has been shown to be an essential leverage to the localisation of international policy agendas, helping to build connections between shared visions, local actions and communities (United Cities and Local Governments, 2023). In fact, the cultural and creative industries are consistently arguing for recognition as a fourth pillar of sustainable development under the broad umbrella of the UN SDG’s (Voices of Culture. Brainstorming Report, 2020⁶)

Fourth, art and culture are critical in deepening our relationship with nature and more than human entities. They can help establish the key values that guide ecosystem living. This connection is not just physical but also deeply cultural, influencing our traditions, knowledge, and artistic expressions. By valuing and incorporating these elements into the mission, we can create more immersive and engaging experiences that resonate deeply with individuals and communities. This approach can help to cultivate a greater sense of responsibility and stewardship towards our environment, encouraging sustainable practices and fostering a profound respect for the natural world. Ultimately, integrating these cultural and artistic

⁶ Voices of Culture. (2021). Culture and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals: Challenges and Opportunities. <https://voicesofculture.eu/wp-content/uploads/2021/02/VoC-Brainstorming-Report-Culture-and-SDGs.pdf> Accessed 30/11/2023

dimensions into the Horizon Europe mission will not only promote environmental sustainability but also enrich the collective European cultural heritage, strengthening our shared identity and vision for a future that is both sustainable and deeply rooted in our diverse cultural experiences.

It follows that the NEB's vision of a cultural movement needs a vibrant cultural and creative sector. The arts and creativity are central to our need to reimagine our built environment beyond business as usual, and for a fair and greener transition that is co-owned by all and that leaves no one behind.

A Mission that places the interconnection between citizens and the built, lived, and natural environments centre stage

We welcome the Working Paper's initial reflections on the challenges, objectives, initiatives, research areas and outcomes of the proposed NEB Mission. However, we also note that there is a predominant focus on the competitiveness and innovation of the construction industry. We therefore ask that the balance is redressed, in order to extend the focus to the intersection of citizens and their lived, natural and built environments. Moreover, many other industries are central to unlocking the potential for more circular and regenerative economies and neighbourhoods, for example the fashion industry, the food industry or health. A narrow focus on the construction industry precludes the NEB from achieving its full potential and engaging a variety of stakeholders and sectors in the transition.

First the working paper states that "the proposed NEB Mission acknowledges that the circularity and the revitalisation of the built environment are closely linked to the cultural dimension of places. In other words, the way we shape our environment as a whole is an expression of our culture, cultural heritage, identity and diversity." (p.6). We find that this statement fails to acknowledge power differentials as well as intersectional inequalities and discrimination. Before benefits to the industry, the needed transition must have positive impacts for citizens, through fair and good employment opportunities, learning and education outcomes, and improvements to living conditions and public spaces and services. We urge the proposed Mission to adopt a postcolonial lens, which problematizes dominant hierarchies in knowledge production and representation among others, in order to reimagine our built and lived environment for a fair and greener transition that leaves no one behind.

Second, the Mission must also reflect the complexities of built environment interventions on the lived and natural environment. Acting on the built environment is framed as a 'silver bullet' in our goal of climate restoration (p.4). Yet there are countless examples of interventions on the built environment that have broken communities and social and cultural ecosystems down. The Tweebosbuurt in Rotterdam is a case in point: the bulldozing and rebuilding of an entire neighbourhood may have made the built environment more sustainable, but it also wiped out community bonds and social capital due to displacement. The proposed mission must acknowledge that displacement and green gentrification are a real threat to our cities' communities and cultures.

Third, we urge the proposed Mission to acknowledge true experimentation and social innovation beyond growth, markets and business models for industry competitiveness.

Finally, we agree that neighbourhoods are the scale at which interventions can impact most. But from our experience, we should also ensure that we do not treat neighbourhoods as laboratories where top-down innovations are implemented. At the same time, we also recognise the importance of having enabling frameworks, infrastructure and policy on city, and country level in order to be successful (and for people not to keep hitting barriers when they try to implement change or upscale their bottom-up projects). Co-ownership and co-design should be at the heart of the proposed Mission. Moreover, the shift in practices and mindsets is not just needed in the neighbourhoods but also in our institutions, ending the colonising attitude towards residents and acknowledging that the best solutions are ones where grassroots communities own the resources and can address the challenges collectively and collaboratively. We recommend that the implementation and further development of the mission keep alive the co-creative spirit that the NEB had in its initial phases involving many different stakeholders in the process and therefore getting stronger results.

Recommendations

Challenge	Objective	Intervention areas	Research Area	Outcomes
Challenge 1: Europe has set a major ambition to be a world leader in green transformation, <u>but how can this transformation be truly regenerative for people and planet?</u>	General objective: Foster a fair, sustainable transition for all, leveraging local cultures and creativity	Acknowledging the role of creativity as a key competence in sustainability transitions	Research alternative learning environments and forms of knowledge production	A transition to a fair, sustainable and beautiful future that leaves no one behind

<p>Challenge 2: Climate change is accelerating, <u>and its impact is most hardly felt by those who experience multiple and intersectional forms of disadvantage and discrimination.</u> The pace of transformation remains too slow.</p>		<p>Foster social innovations that and implement governance models that can balance public and private interests in green and fair transition.</p> <p>Provide tools, services and infrastructure for the common good – inclusive, affordable, safe and accessible for all.</p>	<p>Applying an intersectional and postcolonial lens to climate change transition</p>	
<p>Challenge 3: As climate change deepens existing social and territorial inequalities, it also risks eroding trust in democratic institutions</p>		<p>Invest in cultural infrastructure to help foster civic engagement, democratic participation and social cohesion</p> <p>Support a new set of standards for the development and transformation of living spaces that accounts for citizen ownership and participation.</p>		

Table 1: suggestions for a revised NEB Mission Intervention Logic (based on Joint Research Centre, 2023:11)

References:

- European Commission (2023). Culture and Democracy: the evidence. How citizens' participation in [cultural activities enhances civic engagement, democracy and social cohesion](#).
- Joint Research Centre, European Commission (2022). [GreenComp. The European Sustainability competence framework](#).
- Joint Research Centre, European Commission (2023). [First reflections on building blocks for the design on a possible EU Mission on the New European Bauhaus](#).

A Mission that is about participation and democratic principles

Learning from tradition combined with future-oriented guidelines to comply with climate protection and to create a liveable environment requires new approaches. A worsening climate crisis exacerbates social and political inequalities. NEB is about participation and democratic principles.

Recommendations

- With emphasis on the importance of participation, green transformation should be designed in a socially acceptable way, using examples (case studies).
- For realisable and adaptable CO₂-reductions in the built environment interdisciplinary experimentation coupled (in parts) with grassroots innovation is necessary. Only research on technical issues without also including the social / cultural component is not enough and will fail in realisation. See “Urban Site Development as Temporal Carbon Storage—A Case Study in Germany” as an example of a legitimate and valuable means for the creation of new knowledge (<https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/12/14/5827>).
- What we need is research through implementation projects, focused on transparent analysis and based on common knowledge of the individual local communities, and recognition that this is just as important as basic scientific research.
- The neighbourhood level as a mediating level is exactly the right starting point for implementation.
- It must become clear that much can be changed through culture and that this should definitely accompany quantitative research. Synergies from interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary work are immediately visible - a common sense can only emerge through this.
- In implementation, what is directly visible to people on the ground is important.

A people-centred mission

Do we need a NEB Mission?

The New European Bauhaus lighthouse project for Stavanger (NEB-STAR), with Utrecht and Prague as twinning cities, has now been in operation for one year. During this period, the project has made some discoveries and built up some experiences that influence how we see New European Bauhaus implementation. These discoveries and experiences stem from close contact with citizens, organizations, businesses, social entrepreneurs, coupled with close interaction with local, regional, and national authorities.

NEB-STAR addresses four emblematic challenges:

1. *Challenges linked to the use, preservation and reconversion of existing infrastructure and heritage:* Co-creating a new sense of aesthetics for climate-neutral cities and communities that captures places' unique qualities, history and potential, and generates a sense of belonging, pride and ownership;
2. *Environmental and climate adaptation challenges, environmental and climate risks, prevention and resilience:* Reconnecting with nature to boost resilience and a sense of community, giving new life to the spaces in between buildings through food and nature;
3. *Social challenges (poverty, segregation, social exclusion, etc.):* Creating temporary meeting spaces in urban transition areas, that embrace diversity and strengthen the identity and uniqueness of people and places that need it most;
4. *Economic and territorial changes linked to the green transition:* Co-creating co-benefits for the neighbourhood and city through multi-functional use of spaces and infrastructures

The four emblematic challenges addressed by NEB-STAR align with many of the five Missions that the European Commission has already identified. We can see direct and indirect links to work being done on climate neutrality and the adaptation to climate change, the restoration of our ocean and waters, and to the work being done to transition to more healthy soils. In NEB-STAR as well as the other NEB Lighthouses, we see that NEB is closely intertwined with the 5 Missions. These 5 Missions and the societal challenges they address already have extensive research and innovation programs that will fund innovation and push the transition in wanted directions.

NEB-STAR recommendation:

- **Do not launch a new mission on the New European Bauhaus at this point in time.**
- **Integrate NEB values and principles into the 5 Missions and their Mission Platforms first.**
- **Before launching a potential mission, the current NEB lighthouses should be evaluated.**

The NEB Lighthouse projects are excellent examples of such integration between NEB and the Missions. The way we read the JRC Working Document, it does not seem to build on the experience of the lighthouses and could even be seen to pull in a different direction.

Based on the experiences that the NEB-STAR project has built up during the first year, we recommend that the NEB Lighthouses as well as other projects funded within NEB and the Missions first get evaluated and important experiences and learnings extracted to inform further actions. First after this evaluation, the need for a separate NEB Mission can be assessed.

In case of a NEB Mission

In the European Commission's first reflections on building blocks of the design of a potential New European Bauhaus (NEB) Mission, it reiterates that "The EU missions are designed for addressing complex and interconnected issues" connected to larger societal challenges.

However, the core of the Joint Research Centre's (JRC) working paper seems to revolve much more narrowly and focused around the construction sector, mainly addressing the circular economy, industry, technology, and sustainable materials. This makes it:

- **Too focused on the ongoing renovation wave and construction.**
- **Too far removed from the overall European Green Deal.**
- **Too far removed from other missions and climate action.**

The JRC Working Document appears to give the impression that we can simply build our way out of climate change, when our experience and the science clearly shows this is not feasible.

NEB is intended to link the European Green Deal to our daily lives and living spaces, focusing on the values of sustainability, aesthetics and inclusion. While recognising the importance of the construction sector in promoting Europe's circular and regenerative initiatives, we believe there's more to consider than just focusing on residential buildings and their construction.

Several of the challenges addressed by NEB move beyond neighbourhoods (including circularity) - we would like to see both cities and rural communities addressed to a larger degree if a new mission is to be launched.

A NEB mission should, in our opinion, address whether anything new needs to be built and how other solutions can be developed and thus also promote a more systemic approach to the connection between spaces, people, nature, and the built environment. In short, focus on societal challenges and change.

Social and societal sustainability is currently lacking among the existing 5 Missions, which we believe is a critical aspect to include in a potential NEB Mission. This does not exclude the construction sector or a circular approach, quite the opposite.

Our society is facing a climate crisis, a nature crisis, but also a crisis of polarisation. It all begins with neighbourhoods/communities. This is where lives are lived. And where lives will be affected by the climate transition. However, we should be careful to narrow the mission to just future neighbourhoods, as it might overlook the interconnected nature of the challenges ahead as stated earlier. We should aim to rejuvenate not only neighbourhoods but also commercial areas, infrastructure, and cities at large. While the neighbourhood scale is undeniably significant, we shouldn't underestimate the forthcoming shifts and potential local concerns. Embracing participatory design on a broader scale is vital. In a circular economy (for example), various localities are interconnected through material flows, which could be a

potential source of discord, especially among urban, rural, and peri-urban communities. Therefore, collaboration across different scales—from neighbourhoods to larger administrative regions and across administrative borders—is paramount.

A NEB mission with a too narrow focus on neighbourhoods / communities will not be able to fully demonstrate how the new, climate-neutral lives of the future will be lived. In addition, it will also fail to show in practice how the transition can be just, inclusive, and attractive to all, and in fact even improve our daily lives. This will be counter to the vision of a more sustainable future – for everyone.

A potential new NEB mission should be focused on people and collaboration and can thus serve as a catalyst for other missions. The mission should therefore ensure that the original intentions of NEB remain visible in the mission. This way, we can ensure a mission that truly is creative and transdisciplinary, bridging the world of science and technology, art and culture, and transforming our lives for the better through leveraging on the green and digital challenges. A NEB mission should seek to succeed in addressing complex societal problems through co-creation - which brings us back to what the missions are designed to do.

It is therefore our view, that we need:

- **A mission that focuses on people - the interaction between people, and the interaction between people, nature and the built environment.**
- **A mission that sees people and their neighbourhoods as complex and interconnected spaces, where multiple activities and needs come together.**
- **A mission that strengthens the feeling of inclusiveness and belonging for all in neighbourhoods/communities and can contribute to citizen empowerment.**

Radical Inclusion in R&I

Solutions to tackle inequality and exclusion to support NEB's vision for tomorrow's neighbourhoods

The purpose of this section is to highlight the importance of accessibility, equality, and equity to raise the quality and sustainability of outcomes and joint projects to a new level, and to create opportunities for new perspectives on accessibility and equity.

The NEB Mission aims to revitalise European neighbourhoods with design for sustainability and inclusion. The mission will place inhabitants at the heart of the transformation, providing a horizon for democratic decision-making to tackle citizens' disconnect with implementing the green transition in their neighbourhoods. It will increase ownership and legitimacy and generate the scale needed to catalyse the green transformation in the construction industry, financing models, and on the ground.

The New European Bauhaus initiative is committed to accessibility and inclusion. To ensure that everyone feels safe and respected while participating in the initiative, it is essential to take into account the principles of safer space when working on NEB projects. The development of a New European Bauhaus approach, where all projects and events use the same accessibility mapping, and accessibility plans that describe how accessibility will be achieved in practice, and safer space principles, would have the potential to increase cohesion and transparency in neighbourhoods as well.

With these principles, all participants should have an equal opportunity to make their voices heard. It would bring the New European Bauhaus movement closer to the people and increase ownership, the sense that each of us is responsible for developing our community, preventing climate change, and fighting racism.

Safer space principles include respecting everyone's personal space, listening to others, respecting diversity, and using language that is respectful to all people. By taking these principles into account, NEB projects can be designed with accessibility in mind, ensuring that all buildings are accessible to people with disabilities, that all events are inclusive, and that all digital content and communication are accessible and respectful.

Encouraging participation from diverse communities in all aspects of the initiative is also important. This includes involving people from different cultures, genders, ages, and backgrounds in the design process. Providing training and resources to help partners and stakeholders create more accessible and inclusive spaces can also help achieve this goal. Partnering with organisations that specialise in accessibility and inclusion can ensure that best practices are being followed.

The introduction of accessibility and equality plans and safer space principles in the New European Bauhaus would be a strong example to all European actors of going all out for inclusion and equality and creating opportunities for all, regardless of cultural backgrounds or personal characteristics. No one is left out.

Checklists and guidelines could easily be added to the NEB website for all to use. Safer space principles for the NEB could be created between partners. In order to evaluate the impact of these tools on the working culture, tools on effectiveness are also needed. Making these policies become a natural part of the action will take time, but promoting equality and inclusion is an ongoing process, a long marathon, the results of which will also be visible in everyday encounters as awareness, knowledge, and understanding grows.

The New Bauhaus for global social justice

We now live in a world where all development investment has to acknowledge the reality that top down technology driven and exclusionary Northwest research has not produced the desired impact even with resources that have been spent in the last four decades. Whether it is the work of a "New Bauhaus" (as a global term) or it is any other form of investigation to find solutions for development that have a deep scientific and technological dimension, these processes have to be accountable for new value systems:

1. A private sector worldwide has shown that unless the person who consumes the outcomes of the product or the process is involved in those activities from the beginning, many products and solutions don't produce any impact and find that they are wasteful investments. This is as clear in public development as it is in the private sector and therefore new paradigms of engaging communities of practice are required. The solution beneficiaries must be involved in the process right from the beginning.

2. Increasingly development investments have been guided by professional Northern technology driven and seemingly exclusive institutions that see the upper income markets in the global South as their primary market as the Northern population shrinks. It is the responsibility and the contribution of both elites in the North and the South to recognise the volume of impoverishment and vulnerability that exists today and that is going to grow exponentially in the next two decades as extreme weather events destroy survival habitats. Those are communities with whom new practices, new strategies, new products, and new systems have to be developed.

3. Having witnessed many discussions set up by the Secretariat representatives of the New Bauhaus for industry leaders, there is absolutely no awareness, no knowledge and no sensitivity about the needs of those who are not in the top 35% of income brackets either in the North or the South. This is both dangerous and undermines everybody's commitment to social justice.

4. The New Bauhaus has a strong responsibility to make investments that can proudly acknowledge that these funded processes are set to produce a more equitable world that impacts beyond Europe. Explorations can be made in collaboration with activists deeply committed to issues of equity and qualitative impact-focused strategies in the Global South. Results can impact political and technology leaders in the South who copy what is being done in the North by drawing attention to the development deficits and the climate-linked devastation that we have to prepare for.

A Mission for cultural and societal sustainability tailored to each region

In formulating a response to this working paper, we would like to: a) highlight some elements of the New European Bauhaus vision that are not yet fully crystallised in this document; b) to address a perceived tension in this document, where on the one hand it claims that the new Mission will 'place inhabitants at the heart of the transformation', while on the other, the competitiveness and transformation of the construction industry and built environment take centre stage.

Europe finds itself confronted with a multitude of challenges, accompanied by a burgeoning collective awareness of the depleting state of our planet's finite resources. These realities urgently demand upgrades in actions to expedite a comprehensive transformation. Climate change, the most pressing crisis of our time, cannot be attributed solely to natural forces; it predominantly arises from human activities. In our pursuit of addressing ecological imperatives, we must also design environments that incorporate considerations of cultural and societal sustainability, attained through collaboration across disciplines. The New European Bauhaus emerged as a platform characterised by a holistic mission, offering an encouraging framework for our collective endeavours.

European nations grapple with a litany of issues, including the ominous spectre of extreme climate events, escalating temperatures, the emergence of heat islands, desertification, and prolonged droughts. Simultaneously, they share a rich tapestry of history and diverse cultural heritage that merits safeguarding as they confront these climatic emergencies.

Close collaboration, research and co-design among European nations hold the potential to fortify their collective resilience in the face of shared threats, fostering the development of social and nature-based solutions that are both sustainable and accessible. These solutions must be affordable, inclusive, and imbued with aesthetic sensibilities, aligning harmoniously with the vision articulated by the New European Bauhaus. Aligning shared endeavours in a consolidated mission fosters the operationalisation of these goals.

Environmental challenges, resource utilisation, and inclusive societal solutions necessitate bespoke responses tailored to each region. Adapting policies and actions to congruent climates, ecosystems, cultures, and societal issues, have already been the subject of region-specific platforms, such as NEB of the Mountains, NEB on the Danube, NEB Goes South, Nordic Carbon Neutral NEB, NEB Bauhaus of the Seas Sails, and others.

A Mission that embeds passive strategies and the value of traditional knowledge

- Recent crises have highlighted the need for coordinated collaboration.
- “No-tech” should include recognition of passive strategies and value of traditional knowledge embedded in traditional skills and techniques. It should be defined as “natural resources and utilisation of passive strategies”.
- In addition to building on the European Wood Policy Platform (woodPoP), the Mission can build on other [re]usable and location-specific bio-based materials such as straw/hey, sheep's wool, natural hemp, seaweed, sea shells, etc.
- Instead of stating that we will probably first overshoot, and then work our way back, we should contrast active measures (solar panels, heat recovery systems and technical performance components) with passive measures (orientation, topography, breathable, natural and slow energy exchange materials), when designing or reusing built structure. The ultimate passive measure would be when choosing not to intervene with structure at all (no new building). When working with historic structures and contact zones between old and new, the conservative (conservationist) approach is already accepted, preferring minimal interventions or reversible solutions with a minimal intrusion/alteration. It is important to stress that in parallel to climate change, there is a strong need to reduce waste and wasteful practices which encroach nature, increase pollution and negatively impact on human and animal health and wellbeing.
- “Not leaving anyone behind” will require a location and site specific knowledge and application which takes cognisance of Europe's eight micro-climatic zones and their specificities which are manifested in the traditional knowledge and skills often in evidence in historic building ensembles and infrastructure(s).
- In terms of the General Objective, it is an imperative to put the public interest, people and nature back at the centre of policies and decision-making processes that affect our living environment (see 1 The Architects Council of Europe. Manifesto on the New European Bauhaus. DRAFT Paper for Adoption, October 2023). This will empower and refocus the local authorities to seek and create adequate platforms for citizens' engagement and inclusion in the decision making processes.
- Specific Objective 1: Make Europe's construction ecosystem the world leader in circular and regenerative approaches, delivering key knowledge, technologies, skills, inclusive business models, and jobs for a fair green transition and EU's strategic autonomy with an emphasis on cross-sectoral and cross-disciplinary collaboration.
- The 6th mission will clearly articulate and address the gaps between administrative, technical (environmental) and cultural (societal) space and help mobilise the stakeholders across different sectors and disciplines to engage with a clear common focus. This would enable the participation and applicability of circular economy as an overarching ethos and commitment right down to the practices and methods in the construction sector, maintenance of built structures, demolition and reuse of building material, waste management
- Outcomes under Specific Objective 1: Mapping of the re-use and salvage centres; mapping of the construction demolition waste points and categories; effective and timely waste management for re-use; mapping of secondary and tertiary reuse potential for construction waste; mapping of waste collection hazards and prevention; Digitalisation of construction waste management along the supply chain;

Reduction in demolition (structures and materials) Defining the Re-use guidelines using knowledge from the heritage sector; (Re)defining the role of urban planners, architects, conservation architects, landscape architects, interior architects, designers and artists to embed the circular economy principles in the briefing and design process.

- Research areas under Specific Objective 2: Identify, evaluate and clarify the stages and stakeholders in development process in built environment; Elaborate cradle-to-cradle from micro to macro-level; Map and elaborate governance process from micro (local authority) to macro-level (department, ministry) concerning development process in the built environment, to include inception, feasibility, implementation, follow up, evaluation, maintenance and new briefs.
- Outcomes under Specific Objective 3: Map the system/good practices / challenges / obstacles to allow for an inclusive R&I and investment; Identify gaps and recommend improvements and pilot solutions

A Mission that supports a long-term shift towards regenerative practice and understands the primary importance of dynamic and entangled relationships

Regenerative approaches and processes are increasingly acknowledged for their importance in creating changes that respect the planetary boundaries. In the working paper, this approach is mentioned within Objective 1 – Make Europe’s construction ecosystem the world leader in circular and regenerative approaches. In Desire, we have experimented with regenerative processes in relation to citizens’ involvement and a holistic understanding of transformation of a place, applying regenerative design processes at one of our territorial sites with the aim of letting decisions emerge from carefully listening to the place we inhabit. The outcome has been successful but also with strong points for reflection, especially that regenerative design processes require time.

Based on this, a clear overall recommendation for the NEB Mission is to *allow for lengthy and open processes without estimated outcomes but with curiosity towards what emerges*. Jenny Andersson from the Really Regenerative Centre (partner in Desire) outlines in this article from a personal point of view how Donella Meadow’s interventions for human behaviour can inspire how we work with transformation in Desire (and beyond) and which questions we may find relevant to pose:

<https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/news/desire-and-dancing-with-systems> - some background information about the territorial site referred to can be found through this link:

<https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/sites/kalundborg-circular-campus-kalundborg-denmark>

Challenge 2: Accelerating climate change and the pace of transformation needs to follow

- **Objective 1: Make Europe’s construction ecosystem the world leader in circular and regenerative approaches**

- **Objective 3: Boost public and private investment in R&I, support innovative funding practices and finance new business models**

“Our understanding of value should recognise the primary importance of dynamic and entangled relationships rather than being founded on notions of assets and ownership.” This quote stems from ‘Designing Our Futures: A New European Bauhaus Economy’, an invitation paper developed as part of Desire and aiming at a paradigm shift in how we understand and perceive value. The invitation paper can be found through the following link – the invitation paper will be followed by a White Paper which is expected ready by the spring 2024: https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/assets/uploads/20230707-New-European-Bauhaus-Economy_Digital-version_DML.pdf

The ideas outlined in this invitation paper and further elaborated in the coming White Paper present a fundamentally different perspective on what is needed for transformation at speed and scale. The aim is to support the shift towards a regenerative future for our built environment, and therefore, this paper encompasses more of the challenges and objectives set with the NEB Mission working paper. The recommendation for the NEB Mission can therefore be described as *the need to work with a regenerative understanding of value and to unfold and investigate this notion further through activities that point to concrete and context-based learnings*.

It touches upon a vast array of perspectives: new standards and typologies, material innovation, circularity capacity, adaptive reuse and sharing, new finance infrastructures and redefinition of growth, etc. Each of these and their application in combination calls for further research and investigation, experimentation and exploration within contexts of different scope and scale.

Challenge 3: Deepening existing social and territorial inequalities and risk of eroding trust in democratic institutions

- **Objective 2: People-centred governance of transformation processes**

Transdisciplinary, participatory processes can enable local empowerment by engaging neighbourhoods and bring innovative solutions. Digital solutions ease the interaction between the public and the local authorities by bringing anonymized data that represent sentiments at neighbourhood level – data that can be used further for dialogues between different stakeholder groups.

In Desire, one of our experiments has proved that by using a design framework like the one used by architects in their daily business, in activities that engage groups of citizens with no prior experience with or knowledge of design processes, we see local empowerment, systemic understanding of territorial transformation but also innovative ideas and solutions that bring added values for the involved businesses. The key element here is the interaction between professionals and non-professionals on an equal level where the engagement is based on a mutual perception of the qualities that both types of stakeholders bring to the table. The learnings and outputs are described in this article:

<https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/news/gxn-design-is-not-about-hocus-pocus>

The recommendation for the NEB Mission is to *open for further investigation into the interaction between professionals and non-professionals within transformations in the built environment*. To provide research-based knowledge on potential benefits – economically, socially, environmentally, culturally – but also to analyse impact on a longer term: Do we create better solutions by working in transdisciplinary, participatory processes; what do we mean by 'better solutions', and how do we measure what is better and for whom?

This may fit well with the neighbourhood scale that is emphasised in the working paper. Still a recommendation here may be to consider involving the policy level as well – we risk losing the benefit of local empowerment if the ideas and solutions being brought forward run aground on legislative barriers or inadequate political interest or will to implement them. *The NEB Mission should also include multilevel involvement and engagement* to ensure long-term implementation of proposed solutions and the support and acknowledgement of the legitimacy of local engagement processes.

In this context, the exploration of *digital data and digital tools as means to create involvement and maintain the interest and engagement of citizens* and local stakeholders should be integrated as a key point of interest in the NEB Mission. In *Desire*, we apply a digital tool, Our Walk App, to support citizens' involvement at different sites. It provides unique data but also a starting point for dialogues that support the interest and further engagement. An article describing the use of Our Walk App is available through this link: <https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/news/app-helps-collect-soft-data-in-the-city>

Finally, art as a language that opens to new understandings has the potential of changing our perceptions of places and neighbourhoods. Art used deliberately to create dialogues with local citizens supports a sensitivity to the places we inhabit and creates a sense of belonging and agency that is necessary in our transformation processes. When art is the spoken language, we become open to acknowledging unknown and unseen aspects of our neighbourhoods, to recognizing the existence of other species and their importance seen from a biodiversity perspective.

In *Desire*, art is the key ingredient in activities taking place at one of our territorial sites. The Garden Caretaker is a concept that reinterprets the caretaker role we know so well into a new role with artists listening to a place, to what was before and what is and the different forms of life and artefacts characterising that place:

<https://www.irresistiblecircularity.eu/sites/herlev-asfalt-fabrik-herlev-denmark>

As a movement founded in a perception of the importance of culture to engage and deliver a green transition, the NEB Mission should take *art seriously as a language that opens for new understandings and dialogues*. The role of art as a transformative discipline should be investigated and tested further in new and different contexts, with specific reference to citizens' engagement and people-centred governance.

An entangled, messy, beautiful Mission that is a moonshot like no other

The NEB's broad and diverse adoption across countries, regions, communities in just three years is testament to its value and worth. Since its inception, its strength lies in its rigorous approach to inclusivity – inviting *all* citizens to contribute to its foundation and development. This insistence on co-design and its decentralised network structure – as a means to collaborate on multi-valent solutions to the climate crisis – is novel and precious.

In 2023 over 1400 participants entered the NEB Awards. Transdisciplinary actions, involving over 600 NEB Partners, more than 80 NEB Friends, with reach and impact in all member states, through research, innovation and on-the-ground practice demonstrate the value of a multi-valent approach in addressing the complex, entangled, material, social and ethical challenge of rapid anthropogenic climate change. Instead of “either-or”, a ‘both-and’ approach is needed, that brings together agents and actors from places of all scales, from academia, industry, creative practice, policy. Top down *and* bottom up. Qualitative *and* quantitative.

To date, the NEB as a movement has resisted any hierarchical drive to find single solutions and instead welcomes complexity, risk, mess, plurality of perspectives, allowing in multiple voices and experience to negotiate and co-create resilient pathways that are regenerative by design and in action. The contributions to this paper demonstrate the commitment to resist single reduced positions.

The recent energy crisis in the EU, as an unforeseen outcome of the invasion of Ukraine demonstrated the brittle-ness and lack of resilience of single dependencies and safe assumptions. They can have similarly unforeseen negative ethical, material, social, cultural and natural impacts. Thus a plural, fundamentally democratic, radically inclusive mission is more likely to generate resilient, collaborative, place-specific but scalable and replicable solutions that can be rapidly shared and adopted.

The core question remains: how can we transform from an extractive economy to a regenerative society? Despite recent advances we are still extracting more resources from the planet than we replenish, further extending beyond the planetary boundaries which the planet can sustain. To become circular, we need to replenish at scale, in everything we do, across behaviours, economies, society, politics. In what we eat, what we wear, how we use land, in how we provide for the shelter and the health and well-being of citizens and neighbours.

A dedicated NEB Mission asks us to imagine what this might look and feel like, and how to achieve it. This is a moonshot like no other. It will require all our best minds, our creative intelligence, bolstered by our cultural heritage, local knowledge and skill, as well as tenacity that holds to values of equity in the face of breakdown of social cohesion. This is perhaps our best chance to not only meet the targets of the EU Green Deal, but to design and co-create a better Europe in the process.

A programme that creates a Strategic Blueprint for Sustainable Construction

I. Digitalisation as the key transformation of AECO sector –Architecture Engineering Construction Operation

Value Innovation Platform for Construction 4.0

Types of actions:

Reforms aimed at structural changes, investment in human capital, investment in material capital -such as infrastructures-, investment in intangible capital -such as software, R+D+i, and/or investment in natural capital

One sector that did not industrialise its processes is that of **Construction**, in need of a more important transformation than the other sectors since it is the **most lagging behind in its digitalization**, the one with the **lowest productivity**, the one with the **highest accident rate** and **is not sustainable** in itself.

Therefore, it requires the introduction of this paradigm shift in all the areas that comprise it: starting with the transformation of those who will be its future workers -either from the training field, both from Secondary Education and Vocational Training and in the university and professional environment and with the "push" that will generate a viralisation produced by a television series on the impact of digital on the built-, to the components of its business fabric -both technically and professionally-, through its processes.

It is the implementation of **digitization throughout its value chain**, from the production of raw materials to rehabilitation and deconstruction, adapting software, hardware and workflows to be used in a common and collaborative way by all its agents. It is the only way in this sector to reach **Circular Construction**.

It is needed that a part of resources is allocated to the **conversion and updating** of the laws on which the contracting of works and projects is based, introducing the mandatory use of digitization methodologies for sustainable and competitive industrialization based on digital models (BIM), their programming (Lean), the responsibility of attributions (IPD) and their financing.

II. Objectives

Assessment of the impacts on the economy and future employment

With the actions of digiNEB Construction 4.0 program, the impact on the economy and employment in 5 years will be divided into two axes: the adaptation of existing companies and the creation of new companies.

The proposal foresees the generation of an **increase in GDP in the construction sector and increase in the number of employees**.

The **industrialization of Construction 4.0** contemplates all the stages of the life cycle of a construction -be it building or infrastructure-, from the extraction of materials to create the primary products to the set that allows to "manufacture" a building in a closed, heated, controlled warehouse... understanding that this assembled set can be taken to work and allow its export.

The Construction 4.0 program contemplates from the generation of resources to the **introduction of process change**, attending to the actions of designing, ordering and programming in order to be efficient in all processes for the transformation of a built. A **built asset that will halve its production time, its cost, its placing on the market and its polluting emissions**.

III. Consideration of digiNEB Tractor Macroproject

1. **Europe vision.** *Have a vision of the continent, in the form of transversality and positive impact on other sectors and on the economy as a whole.*
2. **European Semester.** *Respond to the challenges identified by the European Commission, both in the business fabric and in society, so that, if achieved, a leading position can be achieved at a global level, with a focus on employment.*
3. **Double ecological and digital transition.** *Contribute to economic recovery and growth, job creation, the transformation of the productive model in ecological and/or digital terms, the improvement of productivity and social and territorial structuring, mitigating the socioeconomic impact of the crisis and reinforcing cohesion and convergence. All this taking advantage of the opportunities offered by technological advances and innovation processes.*
4. **Leadership.** *Focus on those areas or sectors in which a relevant competitive advantage can be achieved at a global level. In the current international context, uncertain and changing, these projects could also serve to maintain the leading position occupied by our continent in certain areas.*
5. **Reindustrialization.** *Promote the resilience of the European economy, through the creation of new value chains in industry or, where appropriate, improve and modernize existing ones.*
6. **Public-private collaboration.** *Assume the leadership of the projects by the private sector, with the involvement of the affected sectors, but with the firm and determined support of the Administration, so that it finally becomes an exportable project through the EU brand.*
7. **Traction.** *Generate or strengthen collaborative ecosystems involving large, medium and small companies; together with the support of the different public administrations and, if possible, universities and technology centres.*
8. **Scalability.** *Have a rapid scalability that allows an early profit of the actions proposed and a complete execution within the deadlines set by the European Commission.*

9. **Milestones and partial goals.** *Have a focus on continuous improvement through cycles of maturity, with tangible partial achievements from early stages. The achievements of these projects should facilitate significant advances in the competitiveness of the sectors targeting the solutions.*
10. **Continent potential.** *Take advantage of the differential advantages of each country, among which are existing or planned infrastructures, social and cultural characteristics or geographical nature itself, among others.*

Construction as a global entity (it would be better to call it the AECO-F sector, Architecture-Engineering-Construction-Operator and Manufacturer) implies between 8 and 20% of the GDP of any country in the world.

It involves a long list of agents: Public and private developers, urban planners and planners, geographers, cartographers, geologists, topographers, architects and technical architects, industrial, road, civil engineers, public works, builders, contractors, manufacturers, suppliers, installers, all kinds of guilds -painters, plasterers, welders, carpenters...-, maintainers, energy, acoustic, sustainability consultants, project managers, facility managers, and a long etcetera that includes its training entities (vocational training centres and universities), governance (professional associations, associations and guilds). We are talking about changing an entire sector and this automatically becomes a macro-project.

It has been shown that the construction sector is the one that generates more jobs for fewer euros invested and therefore, is the best and safest bet.

Why the Construction 4.0 Strategic Plan for the transformation of the construction sector, is it really a macro-project tractor?

1. Country vision

For its **weight in the country's economy** (8-20% of GDP).

1bis. For its implementation throughout the **territory** and in all the autonomous communities.

1 tris. This is a project based on collaborative resilience without borders between professions, between transnational and trans-sectorial sectors: from agroforestry – the cycle from the very seed of a tree that in 10 years will become raw material of a technological CLT-cross laminated timber wooden structure to the transformation and reuse of manufactured spaces, or the design of a real estate development, through the digitization of three-dimensional models of infrastructures and buildings that make up a city, its activity and its territory.

2. European Semester

The project directly addresses the following challenges of the European Semester:

- i. Delay in the governance structure for public procurement
- ii. Limited success in reducing the use of temporary contracts.
- iii. Introduction of new strategies for the education and training of professionals to alleviate technical skills in the labour market.

- iv. Limited progress in fostering innovation and energy efficiency.
- v. Decrease in labour productivity compared to other continents.
- vi. Innovation below the EU average.
- vii. Low quality employment and qualification.
- viii. A small number of specialists in information and communication technologies.
- ix. Accelerate the transition to decarbonising energy consumption and increasing energy efficiency at the level of buildings and districts.
- x. Territorial cohesion by introducing industrialised productive capacity in rural and peripheral areas.
- xi. Low affordability of housing.
- xii. Valorisation of vocational training, expansion of the range of courses, cooperation with companies and promotion of online.
- xiii. The low use of new technologies by SMEs.
- xiv. Reactivation of the economy, where the construction sector is one of the sectors where the greatest impact can be generated for every euro invested.
- xv. Focus on the European Green Deal on climate neutrality.
- xvi. Work towards a sector based on digital and non-manual technology, improving supply chains.

3. Double ecological and digital transition

The **number of agents** involved in the value chain of this project and the need to harmonise the project within a collaborative environment to make it effective guarantees the approach to this double mission.

The approach is precisely to improve productivity and competitiveness thanks to its digitalization and sustainability.

Because it is the **sector that produces the most damage to the environment** (waste production, zero recyclability, maximum emissions, outdated processes, huge energy consumption, etc.) and needs energy efficiency, decarbonisation of its activity, and a better use of resources.

The project aims to emulate innovative policies of industrial leadership 4.0 and digitalization of benchmark countries such as Finland, United Kingdom, France, Germany and Estonia within the construction sector and innovative production processes that have proven their effectiveness.

The Construction 4.0 project aims to contribute to the generation of new economies by helping to create better housing, better access to housing, with the possibility of recovering materials, and not only generating more resources but also guaranteeing the resources of the future. The digitalization of the sector will help to retrain the group of professionals and technicians involved, creating an environment of greater ease to maintain jobs and guaranteeing their future.

On the creation of new jobs and employment, the creation of new professional profiles, the rehabilitation of current professionals, guaranteeing the inclusion of young people and women is assured.

The transformation of the production model in ecological and/or digital terms is based on four axes: the introduction of wood as a sustainable building material, the introduction of the circular construction criterion, the introduction of DfMA or design for assembly and dismantling, and the introduction of the concept of digital twin for the management of the built environment.

Improving productivity in the construction sector is very easy: construction has a negative productivity dragged down over the last 60 years and at the same time we want to reduce the accident rate on site by removing people from the work by putting them to work in a more controlled space, better climatologically speaking, improving working conditions in a warehouse, however, taking advantage of the opportunities offered by technological advances and BIM, LEAN, IPD and Digital Twin innovation processes, bases of industrialised construction.

4. Leadership

Among the participating entities there is a representative of SMEs, a provider of knowledge and disseminator of acquired and promoted knowledge, a set of backbone entities, and more than one with sufficient organisational technical capacity to carry out the R+D+I activities that the tractor project incorporates.

The aim is to lead the sector to become a new construction export factor.

In the current VUCA international context, uncertain and changing, this project must serve to maintain construction in its leading position that it occupies in our continent.

5. Reindustrialization

Talking about reindustrializing the construction sector is difficult because it can be considered that it is not yet an industrialised sector. Boosting the resilience of the European economy in the field of construction involves first industrialising the sector. It is not a situation specific to Europe since the lack of productivity in the construction sector is something that affects all continents in a general way. Before that, it is time to take the sector to what is called Industrialised Construction, a concept that is achieved through the creation of new value chains in the industry and improving and modernizing existing ones.

The composition of the sector is mainly **99.1% of SMEs** and the SME sector is the target of this action.

6. Public-private partnerships

The creation of a consortium of several entities and companies of all kinds is an example of a transparent and broad collaboration of what can be considered the public-private spectrum of this sector.

The Construction 4.0 Project involves all affected sectors in a plural project, breaking the silos in which the information and communication of each participating agent is found.

7. Traction

The working group, under the form of a digiNEB consortium, is in itself a collaborative ecosystem and an example of the continent's productive panorama.

Large companies with turnover of nearly 2,000 million euros a year to small companies with turnover of 100,000 euros are involved; there are professional associations with more than 100,000 members and there are corporations of less than a hundred; represents all professions in the sector; it is the representative of the municipalities of EU at the same time that regional technology centres appear; and we have universities and faculties of Architecture, Engineering, Economics and Law and also vocational training centres with studies of the Construction range.

The traction that this project will provide is total, it has full **capacity for real sectoral transformation** and therefore should guarantee and multiply the employability effect.

8. Scalability

Because its effects are **medium and long term**, we are talking about the restructuring of an entire sector where the effects should not only be scalable but replicable.

The project contemplates rapid scalability by creating replicability centres in different provinces. This will allow an early benefit from the actions proposed as the improvement of the quality of all the assets built. But at a smaller level, the lower grain would be, for example, the profits generated by winning competitions in other countries, the reduction of consumption bills thanks to energy savings, the improvement of management through digital twins – reduction of pollution, mobility, energy poverty, social, economic and environmental sustainability-...

9. Milestones and partial goals

The strategic project uses the Lean Construction methodology based on TPS to agree actions and objectives with weekly feedback when introducing Kaizen processes of continuous improvement, allowing an Agile pivoting in order to obtain what in the Anglo-Saxon world is known as "low hanging fruits".

The action plan also has monitoring KPIs as monitoring indicators also in order to guarantee the achievements of the project. In fact, each of them must translate into a double-digit advance in the competitiveness of each link in the chain of agents involved. This project only pursues the impact, change and real trans-training of the AECO sector layers a new situation that gives it a future.

The participation of the only segment of the value chain that is industrialized, that of manufacturers of materials, products and construction systems is fundamental in order to take their R+D+i to the entire life cycle of a construction project.

Construction companies must become assemblers, assemblers and technicians in execution processes that guarantee the design processes that architects and engineers conceive.

Digitalization and its implementation must mean a **paradigm shift** as it has been in all other sectors – and that in the architecture, engineering and construction sector has not been accepted or adopted naturally.

10. Continent potential

The benefits of the Construction 4.0 project are not only limited to the companies that participate but also have a social and economic relevance. The project aims to lay the foundations for sustainable growth – integrating economic, environmental and social vectors – in order to give durability to the project. The economic benefits are clear by attributing greater competitiveness to all companies, its effects on public housing, communication infrastructures and city management will be multiplied and the environmental effects will be reflected in the control and minimization of emissions, the improvement of energy management and the use of water and materials.

As a reference from other countries in a similar situation, we find dozens of documents promoting an action similar to the one that this project promotes. It is worth mentioning the latest report by Mark Farmer, entitled "Modernise or die" <https://www.constructionleadershipcouncil.co.uk/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/Farmer-Review.pdf> and with a no less enlightening subtitle: Time to decide the industry's future. The macro-project must be the decision in time to face this challenge.

Professionally, the continent has a long tradition in design architecture, quality manufacturing, vision without borders... And this forms a scenario that allows this turning point.

The project wants to resume the scenario in which the continent was valued as a world reference in design and architecture, now it will have to be in construction and manufacturing, introducing in its methodology the concepts of modular construction, offsite, cradle-to-cradle, industrialised construction, and circular construction.